

THE CONSEQUENCES OF THE "RECONSTRUCTION" POLICY OF THE SOVIET UNION IN THE UZBEK SSR

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Abstract. As a result of the "reconstruction" policy developed by the former Soviet Union, the socio-economic changes that took place in the Uzbek SSR caused the current situation to worsen. As a result, people's dissatisfaction with the authorities increased, and the socio-economic situation of the population worsened.

Key words: 80-90s of the 20th century, content of "reconstruction" policy, transparency, "cotton work", environmental crisis, aggravation of the demographic situation in the republic, "Leninist national policy", political crises, totalitarian policy

Like all republics of the union, the economy of Uzbekistan has developed on the basis of a five-year plan. It was developed by the state and financial authorities at the Center. Five-year plans were approved by the plenums and congresses of the Communist Party and their implementation was mandatory. In many cases, it was not possible to implement such decisions developed in the local conditions. This, in turn, has led to a strain on the workforce and industry. If the tasks that were not given from the center were not carried out, they would be held accountable, and to prevent this, the scope of falsification and additions expanded more and more.

Inattention to social problems, deficiencies in planning, inefficiency of the economy did not satisfy the demands and needs of the population. As a result, the economic situation of ordinary people worsened, and resentment against the USSR increased in the country. By the beginning of the 1980s, agriculture in the republic fell into a very difficult situation. A card system was introduced to provide the population with food. There were long queues.

The activities carried out in the state management based on administrative and command were not focused on the solution of the problems in the society, on the contrary, they deepened the existing situation. The housing problem remained acute. As a result of these negative events, the socio-economic situation began to deteriorate. In late 1988 - early 1989, these difficulties began to increase.

As a result, the financial system collapsed. There was an imbalance in money circulation and finance. It created shortages in all areas of the economy, increased social tension and discontent among people. All these problems, the increase of social tensions in the late 80s and early 90s created very acute and serious problems in Uzbekistan:

- the complexity of the demographic situation in the republic. The analysis of statistical data shows that the total population of the republic increased by 28.8% during the census period, i.e. 1979-1989. By 1991, the country's population increased from 20.7 million people to 386,000 people compared to 1990. This shows that the rate of population growth in Uzbekistan was more than three times higher than the rate of the Union.

However, for many years, this growth of the population was not strengthened by increasing the number of jobs in industry and other sectors of the economy, and by creating the necessary conditions for the livelihood of the population. This led to deterioration of people's living conditions, increase in the number of unemployed, reduction of social labor productivity and income of the population, as a result, decrease in the well-being of the people. As a result, under the influence of the administrative-command system that prevailed for many years in the former Union, Uzbekistan has a backward and fragile economy based only on the supply of raw materials. showed a secret.

During this period, the republic fell far behind the Union average in all main economic and social indicators and fell to one of the last places in the country. As a result of the environmental crisis, 80 percent of women in Karakalpakstan are anemic, or every 2 teenagers called up for military service are physically unfit for service.

As a result of the reduction of all areas of agricultural production except cotton, Uzbeks were turned into cotton-growing farmers. Religious rites were strictly limited, funeral readings, following the dead and other customs were prohibited. Navroz, the ancient, pre-Islamic national-traditional holiday of the peoples of Central Asia, was persecuted. Communist zealots banned Nowruz and invented "Navbahor" holiday instead. However, the Uzbek people did not accept the new holiday "sent down" from above, and the acts of disobedience escalated.

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